

Empowering Youth Through Technical Vocational Education And Training TVET: Upcycling Waste Fabrics For Sustainable Furniture In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria and throughout Africa, the growing amount of garbage from furniture and textiles presents serious environmental problems. High rates of youth unemployment also highlight the pressing need for creative strategies for economic empowerment. This study investigates how upcycling, more especially the conversion of waste textiles into environmentally friendly upholstery for furniture, might be incorporated into Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programs as a means of empowering young people. The program seeks to encourage entrepreneurship, lessen environmental waste, and advance the concepts of the circular economy by giving young people useful, marketable skills in sustainable furniture design and upholstery. The initiative uses indigenous knowledge, local resources, and cooperative relationships to develop scalable models that may be applied to different African situations. Through experiential learning, community-based workshops, and curriculum creation, this method offers marginalized adolescents realistic livelihood choices in addition to addressing ecological sustainability. In the end, the study promotes institutional investment and policy support for TVET as a tactical instrument for equitable growth and green innovation in Africa. The gathered fabric waste was transformed into interior design pieces, including a set of chairbacks, note pads, bags, throw pillows, souvenir kits, unique and stylish jackets, and other items, based on the concept of recycling art. It is expected that these types of projects will educate jobseeker and students about the potential of waste fabrics as less expensive raw materials for a variety of goods, hence assisting in the reduction of waste management issues related to fabric waste.

Keywords: Empowerment, Fabric, Recycle, Textile, TVET, Upcycling and Youth

INTRODUCTION

Upcycling—the imaginative repurposing of discarded materials—offers the youth a practical means of empowerment by giving them the tools to make money and advance their personal growth. Reusing waste materials creatively to create new, valuable goods is known as upcycling, and it has emerged as a crucial tactic in the fight against environmental deterioration and unsustainable waste management techniques in Africa, Nigeria and other part of the globe. All nations and businesses worldwide that are attempting to enhance their environmental performance face both pressure and incentives as a result of globalization. Environmentally friendly products and services, as well as laws, regulations, and policies that promise to have little to no negative impact on the environment are referred to as environmentally friendly (also eco-friendly, nature-friendly, and green) [1]. In order to solve the problem of careless rubbish disposal in Lagos, Nigeria, the research created an artistic approach. This was accomplished by directly reusing waste materials as art supplies (upcycling) and turning waste fabrics into

furniture upholstered substitute (downcycling). Empowering Youth through Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET): Upcycling Waste Fabrics for Sustainable Furniture Upholstery in Nigeria and Africa contributes directly to the theme "Embracing Capacity Building for Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education, Teacher Preparation, and Languages" By focusing on underprivileged and jobless youth, particularly in marginalized regions, it encourages inclusive education by offering them easily accessible training that tackles issues like unemployment and textile waste. Additionally, the strategy promotes teacher training in sustainable practices and green skills, empowering educators to present current, pertinent material that promotes a circular economy. Better comprehension and engagement are ensured when training programs include local languages and culturally appropriate examples, especially in rural or multilingual populations. As a result, the educational process is more efficient and inclusive, producing a generation of young people in Nigeria and Africa who are skilled, independent, and ecologically sensitive.

All things considered, the program is a prime example of how inclusive, skill-based, and locally focused approaches in education and vocational training may promote sustainable development. This initiative enhances capacity building by teaching young people practical skills in upcycling and sustainable furniture making, preparing them for green careers and entrepreneurship. TVET provides kids with hands-on experience in eco-friendly upholstery, promoting both environmental sustainability and economic empowerment

A lot of people confuse circularity with recycling. Upcycling promotes a circular economy and lessens its negative effects on the environment by keeping garbage out of landfills and extending the life of materials. Circular economy runs in a cycle with lot of value chain. You can remake, you can refurbish, you can reuse and then you can also recycle. The ongoing manufacturing of textile waste has been facilitated by rapid fashion cycles, worldwide production scales, and overconsumption [6], [10]. Attending fabrics upcycling courses through Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) may help youth become more independent and in control of their environment, two things that are essential to their empowerment and general well-being. The Africa's commitment to enhancing employability and entrepreneurial skills, especially among youth, is reflected in the advancement of skill development and lifelong learning through initiatives

like the TVET enhancing several benefits for individuals, society, and the economy, including increasing employability, productivity, innovation, and entrepreneurship. In Africa, Nigeria, and many other countries, the importance of TVET in lowering youth unemployment and fostering economic growth is becoming more widely recognized. Less than half of used clothing is gathered for recycling or reuse, and only 1% is made into new clothing because the EU has only recently begun to allow the recycling of clothing into virgin fibers [3] Fig 1. The fashion industry generates a remarkably large amount of waste fabric Fig 2. Upcycling, the creative act of turning waste materials into useful new goods, has become increasingly popular [14]. Upcycling has benefits for the environment as well as for youth, particularly those who are struggling financially. Globally, youth frequently have less access to chances for education, work, and financial gain [10] which may hinder their general well-being and economic independence. In the majority of African and Nigerian societies, fabrics rank among the most significant waste products. According to [17], the terms fabric and cloth are frequently used interchangeably with textile in textile assembly trades like dressmaking and tailoring. The fashion cycle causes styles to become outmoded before textile products reach the end of their useful lives, which leads to waste and overconsumption that is bad for the environment [12]

Fig 1: Cloth Recycling (Haleem et al., 2014)

The majority of these wastes are disposed of or burned. Adding textile waste to a new manufacturing process could boost the value of new products and contribute to sustainable waste management [16]. Upcycling is in line with the worldwide trend toward sustainable practices in which TVET can pioneer to greater height. Upcycling is acknowledged as a way to solve problems and display creativity.

This paper addresses the challenges of creating a sustainable waste management system in the textile industry empowering the youth by concentrating on the reuse of textile waste in the furniture sector from a sustainability perspective. A well-crafted TVET program that employs a problem-solving

Fig 2: Fabric Waste (CALPIRG, 2021)

methodology and instantly applies information and skills might increase youth's understanding of the repressive systems that uphold their helplessness. The TVET system needs to give youth the skills they need to comprehend and evaluate the political, social, and economic structures that control and oppress them. This study looked into producing low-requirement interior fabric materials by converting textile waste into fabric for upholster compositions. This study also postulates to determine the rate at which fabric waste is generated in a few Lagos areas in Nigeria and to pinpoint effective ways to turn the waste into items for upholsters through youth empowerment. The textile manufacturing sector, along with related industries like apparel and fashion, are important socio-economic endeavors that offer numerous

employment opportunities and benefits for the youths in wealth building in terms of income generation [17]. In order to address this, off-cut fabrics were gathered together from textile industry, fashion house and tailoring services. Several private organizations provided the textile waste for the upholstery furniture. A critical analysis is conducted on the issues associated with managing textile waste and applying upcycling processes to waste textiles. Additionally, strategies for utilizing waste textiles to create upcycled items are investigated [13].

Whatever method is used, waste management could be characterized as inadequate due to the detrimental effects on both the environment and human beings. Reusing and recycling textiles is therefore essential to encouraging this creative endeavor. Especially for youths, skill development is a major factor in social and economic empowerment. Better employment prospects, greater income, and financial control, which are essential for economic and societal influence. According to research, skill-development initiatives have benefited the youths in a number of ways.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Despite the development of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) efforts in Nigeria, youth unemployment remains high. Simultaneously, the country faces significant issues from textile and fabric waste, which is frequently dumped into the environment, adding to pollution and unsustainable consumption practices. Although TVET programs are intended to provide young people with useful skills, they are frequently criticized for being outmoded, underfunded, and inadequately aligned with growing opportunities in the green and circular economies. Upcycling waste fabrics for furniture upholstery provides a unique chance to solve these dual concerns by transforming trash into valuable items while also teaching youth practical, income-generating skills. However, there has been little research and experience on how TVET programs in Nigeria might systematically incorporate fabric upcycling into their training curriculum. This gap means that young people are missing out on opportunities to learn long-term skills that can promote entrepreneurship, environmental stewardship, and economic empowerment.

The issue, therefore, is the lack of integration of creative, sustainable processes such as waste fabric upcycling for furniture upholstery inside Nigeria's TVET framework. Without this connection, the potential for reducing waste, empowering youth, and promoting sustainable furniture production is virtually unexplored.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To examine how Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) may empower Nigerian youth by including the upcycling of waste fabrics into sustainable furniture upholstery, thereby encouraging skill acquisition, entrepreneurship, and environmental sustainability with the following objectives;

1. To investigate the current role of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in youth skill development and empowerment in Nigeria.
2. To investigate the viability of upcycling waste fabrics as a sustainable method of furniture upholstery.
3. To assess how including waste fabric upcycling into TVET might foster entrepreneurship and job prospects for Nigerian youth.
4. To assess the environmental benefits of using waste fabric upcycling for sustainable furniture production in Nigeria.
5. To propose solutions for incorporating sustainable techniques like fabric upcycling into TVET courses to increase youth empowerment and green innovation.

RESEARCH QUESTION

1. How do Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) now promote youth skill development and empowerment in Nigeria?
2. How may waste fabric upcycling be used as a sustainable method of furniture upholstery in Nigeria?
3. How can incorporating waste fabric upcycling within TVET foster entrepreneurship and employment prospects for Nigerian youth?
4. What are the potential environmental benefits of using waste fabric upcycling to produce sustainable furniture in Nigeria?
5. What techniques can be devised to incorporate fabric upcycling and other sustainable activities into TVET curricula to promote youth empowerment and innovation?

TEXTILE INDUSTRY

Textiles are vital to our society since they are used in the creation, production, and distribution of yarns and garments, providing us with furniture, shoes, carpets, curtains, clothes, and more. The apparel industry, one of the most important and competitive in the world, supports Africans manufacturing greatly and employs millions of youths in the fields of engineering, technology, and the arts. However, the finished artwork and constructions made from creative trash recycling are the result of artistic waste recycling, and they could be a valuable instrument in the fight against Africa's, Nigeria negligence and rubbish

disposal. Textile production and consumption are extremely globalized, involving billions of consumers and millions of producers globally. The demand for textile goods has continuously increased as the population and economy have grown [18]. According to [13], developing skills raises youth's social standing and promotes community well-being, which in turn leads to financial independence. [15] recognize the value of youth becoming financially independent, but [5] talks about how cultural barriers and a lack of support networks prevent women from developing their skills. The psychological element is cultivating emotions that support individual and collective growth as well as the conviction that accomplishment of change initiatives. Youth can participate in productive activities for financial autonomy when they are economically empowered. The capacity to examine the environment from a political and social perspective is a necessary component of political empowerment. It has been observed that tons of garbage are produced in the textile and fashion industries' efforts to meet the enormous demand for clothing that covers human nakedness.

FABRIC WASTE

In this context, the term "fabric remnant" or "waste" refers to a tiny portion of fabric that remains after the remainder of the fabric has been sold; it typically refers to a small portion, quantity, number, or something similar, a fragment or scrap, a small, unsold or unneeded piece of fabric [17]. After manufacture, fabric remnants are often disposed of as waste. According to [7]. Anything left over or superfluous, such as excess material or byproducts, anything rejected or useless, worthless or unwanted," is what is referred to as waste. [2] looked into the inadequate and improper ways that Nigeria's textile and apparel industry handles its industrial waste. Her studies concentrated on how human health and environmental sanitation in Abeokuta, the capital of Ogun State in southwest Nigeria, were affected by off-cuts and chemical wastes from the clothing and textile industries. The results showed that textiles and fabric wastes have an adverse impact on both the local population and the environment, which is why recycling strategies that work are needed in empowering the youth. Based on the results, suggested starting awareness campaigns with the youth empowerment informing local manufacturers of cloth and textiles about the recycling and management of these wastes. Because it gives them access to resources, control over them, real ownership, and the ability to make and act upon decisions, upcycling entrepreneurship is an essential tool for youth empowerment. Youth may effectively empower themselves through entrepreneurship in a populous country like Nigeria, where unemployment is a major problem. Equal involvement in social,

political, economic, and cultural decision-making results from it.

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND EMPOWERMENT

Youth's entrepreneurship is essential for sustainable development since it promotes shifts in societal perceptions and lessens discrimination. In order to achieve this, obstacles to youth entrepreneurs' advancement must be removed, enabling their full involvement in business endeavors. Youth are now entering and succeeding in a wide range of occupations, such as engineering, trade and industry. In Nigeria, youth are more frequently participating in small-scale entrepreneurship initiatives, utilizing their leisure time and talents to launch and grow enterprises. In addition to producing revenue, these entrepreneurial endeavors improve decision-making skills, which supports family income and general empowerment while handling domestic duties.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

This project is notable because it investigates how Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) can be used to empower adolescents in Nigeria and Africa by upcycling waste fabrics into sustainable furniture upholstery. It emphasizes the potential of green talents in addressing young unemployment, promoting environmental sustainability, and advancing the circular economy. By including upcycling into TVET programs, the study offers a chance to acquire practical, marketable skills while minimizing textile waste. It also helps to drive policy innovation, inclusive education, and sustainable development goals throughout the area.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the research objectives, qualitative study in-depth Interview was selected as an appropriate approach for analysis of the relevant process. This is a method of reviewing works in a systematic, explicit, and reproduceable manner in identifying and critically appraising relevant research. It has been noted that the development of fashion trends and the process by which dressmakers manufacture trendy garments from fabric produce large amounts of off-cuts or scraps, which are piled up to take up space in the workshops in the hopes that they would be useful at some point in the future. Because of the unacceptable state of indiscriminate fabric waste disposal in the nation caused by inadequate waste management practices, as well as the risks these practices pose to public health and the environment, there is a strong case for conducting critical research into the management of fabric remnants, or offcuts, and how they might be turned into interior decorative pieces. When an old furniture is acquired, the fabrics are worn, useless and tattered. Like the typical fashion industry, the outsource outfits produces lots of waste from pieces of fabric cut out in the process of making

dressers. Reports have found that millions of tons of fabrics end up in landfills sites every year. Though concerned, the textile company did not quite know what to do to minimize her waste until they went through the business development training provided by one of their partners, Enterprise Development Centre, (EDC) in Nigeria. The furniture company found it difficult to reuse the old fabrics as the upholster. This now became a problem because the new fabric for the furniture is quite expensive from the market depending on the quality you intended to use. This is what inform this study as a way to look out for off-cut from textile, fashion and tailoring industries to replace the worn-out fabrics from the old furniture. Dressmakers sometimes routinely dump

their off-cut textiles into gutters, especially during rainy seasons. This leads to drainage systems becoming clogged, which periodically causes significant flooding in most communities. When you come to the furniture world, people like African pattern as fabrics. The African pattern cannot be achieved without purchasing new African textile to satisfy the yearning of the customers. This is quite expensive and it is not profitable for the furniture company. Now, thinking outside the box, an initiated agreement is proposed to the textile, fashion and tailoring outfit to pack all the off-cut from their sown and woven clothes, joined them together and package it in yardage Fig 3

Fig 3: Joint Off-Cut in Yards (Susies-Scraps.Com, 2020)

These off-cut were initially thrown away to the landfill which constitute waste and nuisance to the environment. This initiative is one of its kind in the furniture industry where textile waste will

be used as upholster for wooden furniture. The off-cut are cut into equal sizes before joining them to yard length Fig 4

Fig 4: Off-Cut into Equal Sizes (Etsy UK, 2024)

The combination of different colors but quality of the same textile makes it stunning attractive when used as fabrics. This process makes it

unique because is hardly you find such design elsewhere Fig 5

Fig 5: Finished Furniture from The Textile Off-Cut (Jaebee Furniture)

So, this inventiveness makes textile waste as useful as new fabrics for upholsters and youth empower entrepreneurship. The end product of these waste is not only used for fabrics but also

note pads, bags, throw pillows, souvenir kits, unique and stylish jackets, and jumpsuits and now, upholstery for furniture covering Fig 6

Fig 6: Textile Waste into A Variety of Colorful Home Goods

Most of the fabrics used for this exercise are African textile called Ankara in Nigeria dialect. The final product is used occasionally for ecstasy not daily use because of wear and tear of the upholsters These truly African furniture pieces are upholstered from the recovered fabrics from textiles outfits It cannot be used for sofa but can also be used as wall décor. There is what will call

rub count for fabric in furniture world. This means the number of times people sit and rub on a chair before the fabric goes. Rub count is very important in furniture industry because not every fabric can withstand rub count. Fabric mostly used for furniture must be able to withstand rub count test. The limitation for this exercise is technology such as 3d machines that can convert waste clothes to fiber Fig 7.

Fig 7: Recycling machinery (Soumyadeep Saha, 2020)

One advantage of these waste fabrics is that they are easily transformed into new goods that can be utilized until the materials deteriorate to the point where they are suitable for bio grading. Upholsters can create a wide range of goods from these discarded materials'

LIMITATION OF STUDY

This study is hampered by a number of limitations, including a lack of documented data on upcycling techniques within existing TVET programs in Nigeria and Africa. The study may potentially confront difficulties in obtaining key stakeholders and youth participants who are actively interested in sustainable furniture upholstery. Furthermore, differences in TVET infrastructure, funding, and policy support between regions may influence the consistency and generalizability of findings. Time restrictions and a lack of modern methods for practical observation hinder the capacity to thoroughly examine the impact of upcycling in vocational training situations.

CONCLUSION

Youth unemployment and environmental degradation are two urgent issues in Nigeria and throughout Africa that can be effectively and scalable addressed by empowering young people through Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) that integrates upcycling waste fabrics into sustainable furniture upholstery. Young people may develop practical skills, create sustainable livelihoods, and make significant contributions to the circular economy by turning textile waste into useful goods. In addition to meeting urgent socioeconomic and environmental demands, this strategy reframes waste as a resource and skill development as a means of fostering innovation. Multi-sector cooperation, training infrastructure investment, and governmental support are urgently needed to fully fulfill this model's potential. TVET programs that emphasize creativity and sustainability have the potential to be effective instruments for reshaping communities, generating employment, and constructing a more sustainable and inclusive African future if given the proper assistance

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